

Formation Constants of Metal-Chelates of Thioguanine

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The protonation constants of 2-amino-6-mercaptapurine (thioguanine) and the formation constants of its metal chelates with Be(II), Al(III), Cr(III) and UO₂(II) in aqueous media have been determined at 30°. From the values of the constants at various ionic strengths, the values at zero ionic strength have been obtained by extrapolation.

MANY purines have been used in human cancer therapy¹. Most of them are chelating agents, e.g. 8-azaguanine^{2,3} and 6-mercaptapurine⁴. 2-Amino-6-mercaptapurine (Thioguanine; abbr. TGN) also has anticancer properties and a pronounced chelating tendency as well. Metal-chelates of TGN with Mn(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Pb(II) in solution (50% aqueous dioxan) were investigated by Bag, Fernando and Freiser⁵, but chelation reactions with other metal ions have not received attention. Hence the reactions of TGN with the carcinogenic metal ions, Be(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Pb(II) and UO₂(II), as well as with Ca(II) and Mg(II), which are biologically important, have been investigated with a view to collect data on the chelating behaviour of this anticancer drug.

Experimental

The complex equilibria were studied in aqueous media using pH-titration technique as described in earlier publications⁶⁻⁹.

Solutions of nitrates of aluminium (III), chromium (III), copper (II), lead (II), and uranyl (II) were obtained by dissolving their nitrates (all BDH, AnalaR), while in the case of beryllium (II), magnesium (II), and calcium (II), the carbonates were dissolved in known quantities of dilute nitric acid. The solutions were standardised and diluted as necessary.

TGN (Koch-Light) was dissolved in known amounts of alkali, the final concentration of alkali being 0.01M.

Other reagents were prepared as described earlier^{8,9} and the same equipment was used.

All measurements were made at 30°

For the titrations, the final concentrations were: 2.0 × 10⁻⁴ metal ion, 1.0 × 10⁻³M TGN, and 1.0 × 10⁻³ nitric acid, in a total volume of 50 ml. The titrating alkali was 0.1006N KOH.

Results and Discussion

TGN has two dissociable protons and dissociates in two steps, as also supported by the titration curves where the ligand curve is displaced from the acid

curve above a pH 3.7, and shows two inflexions at pH 5.2 and 8.8 respectively. These correspond to the dissociation of the protons from the mercapto- and imino-groups respectively, as follows:

The formation curves which are inverted S-shaped extend from \bar{n}_A 0 to 2 (Fig. 1), confirming the ionization of two protons. The proton-ligand stability constants have been shown in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Proton-Ligand formation curves.
[μ : (A) 0.01M; (B) 0.05M; (C) 0.1M].

In the case of Ca(II) and Mg(II), the chelate curves coincide with the ligand curves indicating no complex formation under the experimental conditions. Also Pb(II) and Cu(II) chelates could not be studied due to precipitation at pH ca. 3.7. Freiser *et al.* studied Pb(II)-TGN chelates in 50% aqueous dioxan medium, while the present studies were in an aqueous

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TABLE I—STABILITY CONSTANTS AT 30°

Ionic strength	log K_n	H ⁺	Be(II)	Al(III)	Cr(III)	UO ₂ (II)
0.10M	log K_1	10.14	8.78	11.49	12.29	11.20
	log K_2	7.57	5.18	9.18	6.82	...
	log K_3	5.75
	log β_n	17.71	13.96	26.42
0.05M	log K_1	10.27	9.42	11.76	12.46	11.32
	log K_2	7.62	5.35	9.76	6.96	...
	log K_3	5.75
	log β_n	17.89	14.77	27.27
0.01M	log K_1	10.32	10.07	12.06	13.00	11.56
	log K_2	7.67	5.58	10.16	7.31	...
	log K_3	6.00
	log β_n	17.99	15.65	28.22
→ 0	log K_1	10.40	10.70	12.40	13.30	11.73
	log K_2	7.70	5.85	10.60	8.30	...
	log K_3	6.15
	log β_n	18.10	16.55	29.15

media. With UO₂(II) and Cr(III) only one and two chelates respectively could be studied, since turbidity appeared above pH 6.6 and 7.5 respectively.

Fig. 2. Metal-ligand formation curves ($\mu = 0.1M$).

The titration curves in other cases could be obtained upto higher pH, and the formation curves had the usual shapes (Fig. 2 for a medium $\mu = 0.1M$; other figs. are omitted).

Studies were carried out at ionic strengths 0.01, 0.05 and 0.1M (using KNO₃) and the values were calculated using the computational methods: (a) interpolation at half \bar{n} values and (b) interpolation at various \bar{n} values and (c) correction term method, whichever were applicable. The values are tabulated.

Extrapolations from log K vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ plots gave the values of log K at zero ionic strength (Fig. 3, a-e).

Fig. 3. Extrapolation of log K to zero ionic concentration: [(a) Proton-ligand system; (b) Be-TGN system; (c) Al-TGN system; (d) UO₂-TGN system; and (e) Cr-TGN system].

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